

ANTIBIOTIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF ESBL *KLEBSIELLA* WOUND ISOLATES IN PATIENTS ATTENDING NATIONAL ORTHOPAEDIC HOSPITAL, ENUGU, NIGERIA

Lilian N. Chukwuma¹, Nneka R. Agbakoba¹, Chidozie V. Udeogu¹, Eucharia A. Dilibe²,
Chukwuemeka O. Arua³

¹Faculty of Medical Laboratory Science, Department of Medical Microbiology and Public Health, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Nnewi, Anambra State.

²Department of Medical laboratory Science and Technology, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Nigeria.

³Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Enugu State University Teaching Hospital, Park lane, Enugu state, Nigeria.

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*Corresponding Author

Lilian N. Chukwuma

Faculty of Medical Laboratory
Science, Department of Medical
Microbiology and Public Health,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Nnewi,
Anambra State.

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ABSTRACT

The antibiotic resistance of microorganisms has been a public health issue due to its role in the dissemination of pathogens as well as mutant and resistant genes in human. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the antibiotics resistance of Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamase (ESBL) *Klebsiella* producers in patients attending clinic in National Orthopaedic Hospital, Enugu, Enugu State, Nigeria. **Methodology:** A Cross sectional study was employed for this research. A total of 230 participants (male and female) of different age groups were recruited using convenient sampling technique. Non duplicate wound swabs were collected from each participant. **Results:** Five *Klebsiella* species isolated were ESBL producers and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was prevalent with 75%, followed by *Klebsiella oxytoca* 10%. The extended spectrum beta lactamase (ESBL) *Klebsiella* producers were identified using the Combination technique and Double synergy of both ESBL and Non ESBL antibiotics. All the ESBL *Klebsiella* producers were

resistant to ampicillin 10 (100%), followed by tetracycline 8 (100%) and imipenem 7 (100%) respectively and the least resistance was amikacin 1 (100%). The double synergy testing of ESBL resistant *Klebsiella* species with Amoxyillin clavulanic acid (AMC) showed no significant difference as $p > 0.990$, while the ESBL resistant *Klebsiella* had a significant difference with Piperacillin tozabactam (TPZ) as $p < 0.001$. The Multiple antibiotics Resistance Index (MARI) of resistant ESBL *Klebsiella* producers was above the normal value of 0.2. **Conclusion:** Extended beta lactamase resistant *Klebsiella* species have been isolated in Orthopaedic wound swabs which contributed to the spread of antibiotics resistance in patient's samples. There is need to adhere to guidelines in antibiotics administration and usage in order to minimize the spread of nosocomial infections and resistant genes. Proper sanitation and personal hygiene is also advocated to aid in proper wound healing.

KEYWORDS: Antimicrobial, Extended spectrum beta lactamase producers, *Klebsiella* species, resistance, susceptibility, wound, multi drug.

INTRODUCTION

Antibiotics resistance has become a global health concern due to its role in the spread of infections and resistant genes which has led to the increase in antibiotics resistance and resistant opportunistic bacteria (Linjing *et al.*, 2023; Ajayi, Akinjogunla, Odeyemi and Owolabi, 2024). This has also led to mortality, morbidity, length of stay in hospitals and economic burden (Chukwuma *et al.*, 2024; Ajayi, Akinjogunla, Odeyemi and Owolabi, 2024). Extended beta lactamases producers are enzymes that confer resistance to most beta lactam antibiotics and monobactam (Hosu, 2021; Suhaila *et al.*, 2023). Bacteria resistance to beta lactam may be due to enzymatic destruction of the antibiotics, altered target or decreased intracellular uptake of the drug (Amela *et al.*, 2023). Beta lactamases hydrolyzes carbapenems, and generates penicillinase. All beta lactamases are selective inhibitors of cell wall synthesis that acts against growing bacteria (Amela *et al.*, 2023; Varshaa and Debasish, 2022). Bacteria that produce beta lactamase enzymes have caused obstruction in activity of antibiotics (Mojisola *et al.*, 2021).

Klebsiella species especially *Klebsiella pneumoniae* can produce beta lactamase enzymes that causes intrinsic resistance which hydrolyze carbapenems and generate penicillinases (Amela *et al.*, 2023; Varshaa and Debasish, 2022). Combined disc and double synergy test have shown to be potent and effective when applied than the use of single antibiotics (Ahmed *et al.*, 2020). Double synergy test was initially designed to detect cefotaxime for oversporing

cephalosporinase and ESBL producers (Mojisola *et al.*, 2021), but due to the plasmid transfer of drug resistant strains of *Klebsiella* species, many researchers have adopted means of handling these emerging resistant drugs using combination therapy; Double synergy or combined disc test to inhibit the resistance (Ahmed *et al.*, 2020; Hosu, 2021). Wound infection has also contributed to public health problem that has led to delay and complications in wound healing, mortality, morbidity, economic burdens and prolong hospitalization (Campos-Madueno *et al.*, 2023; Seiffret *et al.*, 2019).

Jobayer *et al.*, (2021) evaluated the prevalence of Gram negative bacteria ESBL producers and found out that *Klebsiella* species were present with 14.7%, *Escherichia coli*, 19.61%, *Proteus*, 15%, *Enterobacter* species and *Acinetobacter* species with 30%. They were also subjected to antibiotics carbapenems that proved effective against *E.coli*, *Klebsiella* species, *Proteus* species and *Acinetobacter* species (Mohammed *et al.*, 2021).

A meta-analysis of ESBL *Klebsiella pneumoniae* by Shyaula *et al.*, (2023) provided a high resistance towards routine drugs. Shyaula in his work noted that *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was highly resistant towards ampicillin with 99.9% and ESBL producing strains of *Klebsiella* was found to be effective to imipenems with 99%, followed by amikacin 92.7% (Ahmed *et al.*, 2020). The purpose of this study was to determine the antimicrobial susceptibility of ESBL *Klebsiella* producers in wound swabs of participants using conventional method.

Plate 1: ESBL testing using Double synergy test.

Plate 2: Combination testing with both ESBL and Non ESBL antibiotics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area: Study area is Enugu in Enugu State. Enugu State has population density rated at 460km². Enugu State was popularly known as Coal city due to its minning in the past. National Orthopaedic Specialist Hospital Enugu is situated at Abakpa junction, Abakaliki road, Enugu that covers the South East region.

Study setting and design; A Cross sectional study was used for this research. Conventional method was used for the assessment of *Klebsiella* species in wound. Antimicrobial susceptibility was done with single disc of ESBL, non ESBL antibiotics and ESBL inhibitor using Kirby Bauer technique. Combination and double synergy testing was also used for the assessment.

Study population, subject selection and criteria; The study population consists of 230 participants (male and female) of different age groups with wounds in National Orthopaedic Hospital, Enugu, Enugu State, Nigeria.

Sample size determination; Naing's sample size determination formula was used for this research (Naing *et al.*, 2005). Calculation formula: $N = z^2 \times p(1-p) / d^2$

N=minimum sample size

P=prevalence of pathogenic bacteria isolates in wound (82%), (Aisha *et al.*, 2013).

D=desired level of significance=0.05 (5%), Z= the level of statistical significance of the expected result, in this case 1.96 for 95%. confidence interval= **1.96 (95%) C.I**, $N = 1.96^2 \times 0.82(1-0.82) / 0.05^2 = 227 \cong 230$ participants. A total of 230 samples were used for this study.

Ethical consideration: The ethical approval was obtained from the Ethical Committee National Orthopaedic Hospital, Enugu.

Sampling Technique: Convenient sampling technique was used in the collection of patient's samples during clinical hours. Individual participant was voluntary and the purpose of the sample collection was made known to them before collection.

Sample collection and demographic: Wound samples were collected from participants that met the criteria in National Orthopaedic Specialist Hospital, Enugu. Questionnaires was

extracted from the Literature review and information obtained from their folders and socio demographic data was captured such as age, sex, gender, duration of wound stage and others.

Laboratory analysis of specimen

Wound swabs were cultured in different media; MacConkey agar, blood agar, chocolate agar, nutrient agar, nutrient broth and chromatic detection agar. The bacteria isolate identification was done with APIZ 20 E, Enterosystem 18R, TSIA agar test, Gram stain as well as other biochemical routine tests. The test organisms were emulsified from the overnight pure colonies of the bacteria isolates in sterile saline solution and compared with the equivalence standard of 0.5McFarlands turbidity. The turbidity standard was prepared by mixing 99.5mls of 1% sulphuric acid and 0.5mls of 0.048M Barium chloride solution and vortex for 2mins (Founou *et al.*, 2018).

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) was done for all the bacteria isolates using Muller Hinton agar. Kirby-Bauer method was employed according to recommended guidelines by Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI, 2020). Commercially available single discs antibiotics (Biorapid, France) were used for the analysis: Ciproflaxacin (1µg), Ampicillin (10µg), Doxycyline (10µg), Tetracycline (5µg), Imipenem (10µg), Amikacin (30µg), Ceftriazone (30µg), Oxacillin (5µg), Amoxycillin clavulanic acid (30µg), Piperacilin tazobactam (85µg).

The diluted overnight broth cultures of the isolates were spread on the Muller Hinton media in a lawn form and allowed for five minutes (5mins) before applying on it, (10) ten different antibiotics. They were incubated overnight at 35°C. The *Klebsiella* strains that were Multidrug resistant (those that were resistant to more three classes of antibiotics) and ESBL *Klebsiella* producers (those that were resistant to beta lactam antibiotics) were read. Non beta lactam antibiotics were also applied to the ESBL *Klebsiella* producers. Eight (8) panels of different classes of antibiotics were used for combination method as seen in Plate 2. This was done by placing each antibiotic, 20mm apart, while two antibiotics panels were used as ESBL inhibitors for double disc synergy testing of ESBL *Klebsiella* resistant strains as seen in Plate 1.

The resistant ESBL *Klebsiella* strains from the different ESBL antibiotics were analyzed with Amoxycillin clavulanic acid and Piperacilin tazobactam respectively by applying the ESBL inhibitors separately each 20mm apart (center to center) on the Muller Hinton agar plates.

Klebsiella pneumoniae ATCC 13883 was used as positive quality control. The plates were read by checking for inhibition. Sensitivity pattern was read according to the interpretive guidelines published by the National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards (CLIS, 2020).

The inhibition diameter of the control strains with reference standard were compared with that of the test organisms on the agar plate for “Susceptibility, Intermediate and Resistant”, published by the National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards. The Determination of Multiple Antibiotic Resistance Index (MARI) of the ESBL was calculated using the method of Ayandele *et al.*, (2020) for measurement of the antibiotic resistant by dividing the number of antibiotics that are resistant by the total number of antibiotics tested. The tested organisms were compared with those of the control strains with reference to the corresponding minimum inhibitory concentration and interpretive guidelines published by the National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards.

RESULTS

The distribution of ESBL *Klebsiella* producers in wound swab; *Klebsiella pneumoniae* had the highest ESBL rate of 15 (75%) *Klebsiella oxytoca* 2 (10%) *Klebsiella michiganensis*, *Klebsiella ozaenae* and *Klebsiella aerogenes* had ESBL of 1 (5%) (Table 1).

The Resistance of ESBL *Klebsiella* producers was highest with Ampicillin, n=10, followed by Tetracycline, n=8, Imipenem, n=7, Oxacillin, n=6, Doxycycline, n=4, Ceftriazone, n=4, and the least was Amikacin, n=1 (Figure 1).

The frequency of resistant ESBL *Klebsiella* producers with Ampicillin was highest in *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, followed by *Klebsiella oxytoca* and the least *Klebsiella ozaenae* (Figure 2).

The MAR index of ESBL *Klebsiella* producers was dominant in *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, 0.63, followed by *Klebsiella oxytoca*, 0.14, the least was *Klebsiella michiganensis* and *Klebsiella ozaenae* 0.06 respectively (Table 3).

The resistant ESBL *Klebsiella* producers tested with ceftriazone was (n=13), Ampicillin (n=12), Imipenem (n=9), Oxacillin (n=2), when it was tested with ESBL inhibitor; (Amoxicillin clavulanic acid) using double synergy test, ceftriazone resistant ESBL *Klebsiella* had 3 (23.1%) susceptibility rate with AMC, ampicillin resistant ESBL *Klebsiella*

had 2 (16.7%), imipenem resistant ESBL *Klebsiella* had 2(16.7%), and oxacillin resistant ESBL *Klebsiella* had 1 (14.3%) susceptibility rate respectively. There was no significant difference in the susceptibility, and resistant pattern of ESBL *Klebsiella* producers with the AMC as p 0.990.

The ESBL *Klebsiella* producers tested with ceftriazone had resistance of (n=9), ampicillin (n=11), imipenem (n=9), oxacillin (n=5). When it was tested with ESBL inhibitor; Piperacillin tazobactam (TPZ) using double synergy test; Ceftriazone resistant ESBL *Klebsiella* producer had 7 (77.8%) susceptibility rate, oxacillin 5 (14.3%), ampicillin 1 (9.1%) and no susceptibility with imipenem. There was a significant difference with the (TPZ) as $p < 0.001$.

DISCUSSION

ESBL *Klebsiella* species was analyzed with different classes of antibiotics; *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, exhibited a high resistance especially in ampicillin and imipenem and more sensitive to ceftriazone on Muller Hinton agar respectively using Kirby Bauer technique. Most of the results obtained were related with other authors as provided by Jobayer *al.*, (2021); Mohammed *et al.*, (2021); Moro *et al.*, (2018). ESBL *Klebsiella* species was sensitive to ciprofloxacin which is a non ESBL antibiotics; a likely suggestion may be due to its inhibition on bacteria DNA and growth of *Klebsiella* species as reported by Ashurst Dawson (2023).

The Multiple antibiotics resistant index (MARI) of *Klebsiella* species in ESBL exceeded the normal value of less than 0.2 especially in *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, followed by *Klebsiella ozanae*. The MAR index of ESBL *Klebsiella* species with ampicillin and imipenem had a high resistant index than with the oxacillin and ceftriazone respectively.

The Amoxicillin clavulanic acid (AMC) seems to be more effective as observed in the reactions of ampicillin and imipenems than with the Piperacillin tazobactam (TPZ). A likely explanation may be that the AMC and TPZ were able to inhibit the action of the beta lactamase enzymes with the *Klebsiella* ESBL producers. These authors reported on ESBL inhibitors with similar and variable results; Ahmed *et al.*, (2020); Fonou *et al.*, (2018); Hosu (2021).

Table 1: Distribution of ESBL *Klebsiella* producers in Wound Swab.

Isolates	ESBL	(%)
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	15	75
<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	2	10
<i>Klebsiella ozaenae</i>	1	5
<i>Klebsiella aerogenes</i>	1	5
<i>Klebsiella michiganensis</i>	1	5
	n=20	(100%)

Figure 1: Overall Pattern of Susceptibility/Resistant ESBL *Klebsiella* producers.

Figure 2: Bar chart representing the frequency of resistant ampicillin with *Klebsiella* ESBL isolates.

Table 3: Multiple Antibiotics Resistant of ESBL *Klebsiella* Production (MAR index) n=45.

Antibiotics	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	<i>K.michiganensis</i>	<i>K.oxytoca</i>	<i>K.ozaenae</i>	<i>K.aerogenes</i>	Total
Ciprofloxacin	1(0.02)	1(0.02)	0(0.00)	1(0.02)	1(0.02)	4(0.08)
Ampicillin	7(0.16)	0 (0.00)	1(0.02)	1(0.02)	0(0.00)	9(0.20)
Impenem	4(0.09)	0 (0.00)	2(0.04)	1(0.02)	0(0.00)	7(0.15)
Tetracycline	3(0.07)	0 (0.00)	1(0.02)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	4(0.09)

Ceftriazone	3(0.07)	0 (0.00)	1(0.02)	0(0.00)	1(0.02)	5(0.11)
Doxyclyline	2(0.04)	0 (0.00)	0(0.00)	1(0.02)	0(0.00)	3(0.06)
Amikacin	4(0.09)	1(0.02)	1(0.02)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	6(0.13)
Oxacillin	4(0.09)	1(0.02)	1(0.02)	0(0.00)	1(0.02)	7(0.15)
	0.63	0.06	0.14	0.08	0.06	0.97

MARI value 0.2 is significant.

Table 4: ESBL Antibiotics Susceptibility / Resistant Pattern with ESBL inhibitor (Amoxycillin Clavulanic Acid) among *Klebsiella* Species using Double Synergy Test.

Susceptibility and Resistant Pattern.

ESBL Antibiotics	Susceptible (n=8)	Intermediate (n=8)	Resistant (n=25)	$\chi^2 = 0.874, df=6,$
Ampicillin (n=12)	2 (16.7%)	2 (16.7%)	8 (66.7%)	$p=0.990$
Imipenem (n=9)	2 (22.2%)	2 (22.2%)	5 (55.6%)	
Ceftriazone (n=13)	3 (23.1%)	3 (23.1%)	7 (53.8%)	
Oxacillin (n=7)	1 (14.3%)	1 (14.3%)	5 (71.4%)	

ESBL Antibiotics / Susceptible /intermediate /resistant Pattern with ESBL inhibitor (TPZ) among *Klebsiella* Species using Double Synergy Test

Susceptibility and Resistant pattern

ESBL Antibiotics	Susceptible (n=13)	Resistant (n=21)	$\chi^2=23.564, df=6,$
Ampicillin (n=11)	1(9.1%)	10(90.9%)	$p<0.001*$
Imipenem (n=9)	0(0.0%)	9(100%)	
Ceftriazone (n=9)	7(77.8%)	2(22.2%)	
Oxacillin (n=5)	5(14.3%)	0(71.4%)	

Limitations of the study

A cross –sectional study was used in this study with the participants, there was no further feedback obtained from the participants after sample collection.

CONCLUSION

This study provides information on the frequency distribution, prevalence and ESBL resistance and susceptibility of *Klebsiella* species in wound infection using conventional method. The findings showed that ESBL *Klebsiella* species are prevalent and have caused a remarkable role in the antibiotics resistance due to the production of beta lactamase enzymes that contributes to poor wound healing and spread of nosocomial and opportunistic infections in the hospital environment.

The MAR index exceeded the normal value in ESBL *Klebsiella* species. The study has provided information on ESBL *Klebsiella* species multiple resistance with different routine and current ESBL antibiotics. Some of the ESBL and non ESBL antibiotics are still effective to be used in the treatment of wound infections such as ceftriaxone and ciprofloxacin. The Amoxicillin clavulanic acid showed a greater inhibition than Piperacillin tozabactam in the testing of ESBL resistant *Klebsiella* species using the double synergy test.

There is need for adherence in the use of antibiotics prescription by health practitioners and patients.

RECOMMENDATION

Continuous review and re-evaluation of routine drugs for proper treatment of ESBL *Klebsiella* species in wound infections are necessary. Conventional method of testing antimicrobial drugs can be employed on *Klebsiella* species in wound samples.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmed, A.A., Nusrat, A.J., Ali Hassan, S.M and Mohammed, Z.A. (2020). Microbiological screening of antimicrobial sensitivity profiling of wound infections in Tertiary care Hospital of Bangladesh. *European Journal of Medical and Health Sciences*, 2(5): 100- 106.
2. Aisha, M., Gbonjubola, O.A and Yakubu, K.I. (2013). Incidence and antibiotics susceptibility pattern of bacterial isolates from wound infections in a Tertiary hospital in Nigeria. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 12(4): 617-621.
3. Ajayi, A., Akinjogulna, O.J., Odeyemi, A.T and Owolabi, A.O (2024). Role of plasmids in antibiotic resistance in a clinical infections and implications for epidemiology surveillance: A review. *All Life*, 17(1): 2350414.
4. Amela, D.L., Dana, G., Ema, H., Dzemilja, Azra, C.L., Seijla, K.K and Svjetiana, L.Z. (2023). A Retrospective study conducted from Nov. 2020-2021 using Standard Laboratory methods for detection of ESBL and Carbapenemase production using phenotypic methods and combined disc test with various inhibitors. *Saudi Medical Journal*, 44: 8.
5. Ashurst, J.V and Dawson, A. (2023). *Klebsiella pneumonia* In: Stat Pearls, internet Treasure Island (FL) Stat pearls publishing, Jan 2024; <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/wbk51900>.

6. Ayandele, AA., Oladipo, EK., Oyebisi, O and Kaka, MO. (2020). Prevalence of Multi antibiotics Resistant *E.coli* and *Klebsiella* species obtained from a Tertiary Medical Institution in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Qatar Medical Journal*, 2020; (1): 9.
7. Campos –Madueno, E., Aline I.M., Keller, P.M., Andrea, E., Vincent, P., Laurent, P and Patrice, N.(2023). Evaluation of phenotypic tests to detect extended spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL) producing *Klebsiella oxytoca* complex strains. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*, 61(4): e0170622.
8. Chukwuma, L.N., Agbakoba, N.R., Enweani, I.B., Udeogu, V.C., Arua, C.O. and Dilibe, C.L. (2024). Inflammatory Cytokines levels in Patient's Serum and Its Relation to the duration of Wound Healing in Orthopaedic Hospital Enugu, Nigeria. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 130(6): 1008-1018.
9. Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute (C.L.S.L) (2020). Performance standards for antimicrobial susceptibility testing; 30th informational supplement. Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute, document (M100-530).
10. Founou, R. C., Founou, L. L and Essack, S. Y. (2018). Extended spectrum beta-lactamase mediated resistance in carriage and clinical gram-negative ESKAPE bacteria: a comparative study between a district and tertiary hospital in South Africa. *Antimicrobial Resistance Infection Control*, 7: 134.
11. Hosu, M.C., Vasaikar, S.D, Apalata, T and Okuthe, G.E. (2021). Detection of extended spectrum beta- lactamase genes in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from patients in rural Eastern Cape Province, South Africa. *Scientific Report*, 11: 7110.
12. Jobayer, M., Mizanur, R., Nadira, A., Naomee, S., Rubina, A and Suzzanam, SM. (2021). Organisms isolated from wound swab and pus with their antibiotics susceptibility pattern in a tertiary care hospital of Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Medical Research Council Bulletin*, 47: 181.
13. Linjing, W., Haijun, C., Wanting, L., Ling, Y., Zhenbo, Xu and Dingglang, C. (2023). Resistome and Genome analysis of an Extensively Drug resistant *Klebsiella michiganensis* KM1BJ106-1 Characterization of a novel *Klebsiella pneumoniae* carbapenemase plasmid pB106-IMP harbouring blaIMP-4 and blaSHV-12. *Antibiotics (Basel)*, 2023; 12(9): 1463.
14. Mohammed, J.G., Javad, Z., Parisa, R.A., Zahra, Y., Masoud, S and Niloufar, R. (2021). Comprehensive study of antimicrobial susceptibility pattern and extended spectrum beta lactamase (ESBL) prevalence in bacteria isolated from urine samples. *Scientific Reports*, 11: 518.

15. Mojisola, C. H., Vasaikar, S. D., Okuthe, G.E and Apalata, T. (2021). Detection of extended spectrum beta-lactamase genes in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from patients in rural Eastern Cape Province, South Africa *Scientific Reports*, 11: 7110.
16. Moro, D. D., Bello, H.O and Akano, S.O. (2018). Incidence and Antibiotic Resistance pattern of Bacteria Associated with wound infection in some Hospitals in Lagos, *Nigeria Asian Journal of Applied Science*, (6)4: 199-303.
17. Naing, L., Winn, T and Rusli, B.N. (2005). Practical issues in calculating the samples size for prevalence studies. *Architecture Orofacial Science*, 1: 9-14.
18. Seiffret, S.N., Wuthruh, D., Gerth, Y., Egil, A., Kohler, P and Noite, O. (2019). First case of KPC-3-producing michiganensis in Europe. *Journal of New Microbes New Infection*, 29: 100516.
19. Shyaula, M. Khadka, C., Dawadi, P and Banjara, M.R. (2023). Systematic Review and Meta- analysis on Extended-Spectrum β -lactamases producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in Nepal. *Journal of Microbiology Insights*, 16: 1-13.
20. Varshaa, A and Debasish, K (2022). Biochemical exploration of β lactamase inhibitors. *Frontier Genetics, Computational Genomics*, 13: 2022.
21. World Health Organization (WHO)(2023). Antimicrobial Resistance. [Htps://www/who](https://www/who) International. Retrieved, 2024; 18 June.